

Survey targeting the HACCP-based self-control programs

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Survey on the microbiological sampling and analysis in the HACCP self-control programs

Dear Colleague,

As part of the One Health Integrative Action, the One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants (OH-Harmony-CAP) project, we are undertaking an OHLabCap survey targeting food business operators HACCP-based self-control programs.

This is an important data collection exercise to help describe the One Health microbiology system by surveying food laboratories across all EU/EEA countries. We will use this information to identify gaps and needs necessary to develop and implement harmonised and compatible protocols for the detection and typing of foodborne pathogens across One Health. For more information, please visit the One-Harmony-CAP website (<https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>).

The project will collect information on six priority bacteria and five priority parasites:

1. *Campylobacter* spp.
2. *Listeria monocytogenes*
3. *Salmonella* spp.
4. Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC)
5. *Shigella* spp.
6. *Yersinia* spp.

1. *Cryptosporidium* spp.

2. *Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)*
3. *Echinococcus multilocularis*
4. *Toxoplasma gondii*
5. *Trichinella* spp.

To provide an overview, of the sampling and analyses that are performed on behalf of our food business operators HACCP-based self-control programs, the One Health EJP Joint Integrative Project OH-Harmony-CAP has included this optional online survey. Due to the lack of knowledge and overview of how many samples that are taken and processed by the food business operators, we would appreciate your contribution by filling in this survey focused on these public health relevant microorganisms.

Note: Participation in this survey is anonymous. The gathered information will be included in a technical report and the results of this survey will be open source data and will be published on <https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>. Data will not be used for commercial purposes.

For more information on the One Health EJP Joint Integrative Project OH-Harmony-CAP please visit the projects website <https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>

Thank you for your contribution!

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Swedish Food Agency

And

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Coordinators of One Health EJP Joint Integrative Project, OH-Harmony-CAP

Instructions for filling out the survey

Due to the wide scope across questions, the survey may require more than one person to fill it out. If needed, the survey can, at any point, be saved and shared between colleagues so that the responsible person(s) for each of the priority bacteria and parasites can respond.

1. If you need to share the survey link with your colleagues, follow the steps as described in the invitation email.
2. Fill out the survey on the basis of your laboratory and/or institute.
3. Only data from food business operators self-control programs (i.e. do not include samples from official surveillance programs and/or surveillance samples or samples from research projects)
4. The average time to fill out the survey is 15 minutes (time to collect data for the answers)

not included).

The deadline for filling out the survey is June 25, 2021

Survey on the microbiological analyses within the HACCP-based self-control programs

Note, please answer the following questions on the basis of what is being processes and analysed only in your laboratory

* 1. Select the food category/food area of the samples analyzed in your laboratory.

(If applicable, select more than one option)

- Dairy products
- Fish and seafood
- Meat and products thereof
- Vegetable and fruits and products thereof
- Bakery products
- Egg products
- Beverages
- Ready-to-eat mixed meals
- Food processing area, environmental surfaces
- Other processed food and prepared dishes
- Broiler carcasses
- Pig carcasses
- Cattle carcasses
- Other

1a. Please indicate the food category.

	Ready-to-eat	Non Ready-to-eat
* Dairy products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Fish and seafood	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Meat and products thereof	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Vegetable and fruits and products thereof	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Bakery products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Egg products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 2 . Which of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites does your laboratory analyse?

(If applicable, select more than one option)

- Campylobacter* spp.
- Listeria monocytogenes*
- Salmonella* spp.

- Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC)
- Shigella* spp.
- Yersinia* spp.
- Cryptosporidium* spp.
- Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)*
- Echinococcus multilocularis*
- Toxoplasma gondii*
- Trichinella* spp.
- NA

2a. How many samples did your laboratory analyze (mean of the last 3 years: 2018, 2019, 2020)?

(Note: If your laboratory does not analyse a particular pathogen then please write "NA")

	Number of samples (mean of the last 3 years)
* <i>Campylobacter spp.</i>	
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	
* <i>Salmonella spp.</i>	
* <i>Shiga toxin-producing E. coli (STEC)</i>	
* <i>Shigella spp.</i>	
* <i>Yersinia spp.</i>	
* <i>Cryptosporidium spp.</i>	
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	
* <i>Trichinella spp.</i>	

2b. How many positive samples did your laboratory analyse (mean of the last 3 years: 2018, 2019, 2020)?

(Note: If your laboratory does not analyse a particular pathogen then please write "NA")

	Number of samples (mean of the last 3 years)
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> (<i>sensu lato</i>)	
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	

3. Does your laboratory use ISO standards for the detection of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3a. If yes, is your laboratory accredited for the utilised ISO standard?

	Accreditation, yes	Accreditation, no	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Does your laboratory use alternative methods for the detection of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites?

	Yes	No	NA
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4a. If yes, is your laboratory accredited for that method?

	Accreditation, yes	Accreditation, no	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4b. Please specify the alternative method your laboratory uses for the detection of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites.

(Note: If your laboratory does not analyse a particular pathogen then please write "NA")

	Alternative method
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	
Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	

<i>Shigella</i> spp.	
<i>Yersinia</i> spp.	
<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	
<i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	
<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	
<i>Trichinella</i> spp.	

5. Do you send out any of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites for external analysis?

	Yes	No	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6. In case of positive samples, does your laboratory store the six priority bacteria (i.e. isolates or DNA) and five priority parasites?

	Stored	Not stored	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6a. How long does you laboratory store the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites?

	< Six months	Six months	One year	> One year
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. Does your laboratory characterize/type the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites *i.e.* molecular, microscopy, sero- and/or biochemically

- Yes
- Occasionally
- No

7a. Which methods does your laboratory use for typing of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites?

(If applicable, select more than one option)

	Antibiotic typing	Microscopy	Serotyping	PFGE	MLVA	PCR /RT-PCR	MLST	MALDI-TOF	WGS	Other	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> (<i>sensu lato</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>										
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>										

PFGE: Pulsed-Field Gel Electrophoresis

MLVA: Multilocus Variable number tandem repeat Analysis

PCR/RT-PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction/Real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction

MLST: Multilocus Sequence Typing

MALDI-TOF: Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight

WGS: Whole Genome Sequencing

* 8. Does your laboratory participate in external quality assessments/proficiency tests?

- Yes
- No

8a. For which of the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites, does your laboratory take part in external quality assessments or proficiency tests?

	Proficiency tests	NA
* <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Shiga toxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Shigella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Yersinia</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Echinococcus granulosus (sensu lato)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* <i>Trichinella</i> spp.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 9. Which proportion of the total work carried out in your laboratory represents the analysis on the six priority bacteria and five priority parasites?

- ≤ 30%
- 31-60%
- 61-80%
- 81-100%

Contact information

Note: This contact information will not be shown in the final report.

Name of laboratory

(Not mandatory)

* Country

Email address

(Not mandatory)

Final Comments

Is there anything else you wish to add to the information you have provided?

1000 character(s) maximum

Acknowledgement

Thank you for your participation!

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